

Numerical Investigation of Effects of Nanofluids and Swirling Jets a Heated Surface sensor

Afsin Gungor^{1*}

¹Bucak Technology Faculty, Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University, Turkey

ARTICLE: INFO

Keywords:

Computational Fluid Dynamics, Inlet temperature, Nanofluid, Swirling Jet.

History:

Received 04 February 2025

Accepted 23 February 2025

Published 27 February 2025

ABSTRACT

Heat loads of new technology electronic devices have been a main problem for new technological improvement. So, enhancing heat transfer is a critical key to solve this problem. The present study is focused on the numerical investigation of heat transfer from a heated surface by using nanofluids and swirling jets. Effects of different Reynolds number ($Re=12000, 15000, 18000, 21000$) and effects of different inlet temperature ($T_{inlet}=5, 10, 20, 30^{\circ}C$) on heat transfer and fluid flow were studied numerically. $Al_2O_3-H_2O$ nanofluid was used as a base coolant for all parameters. $k-\omega$ turbulent model of PHOENICS computational fluid dynamics code was used for numerical analysis. It was obtained that increasing Reynolds number causes an increase in the average Nusselt number and decrease in surface temperature. So, increasing Reynolds number from $Re=12000$ to 21000 causes an increase of 51.3% on average Nusselt Number. Thermal boundary region does not occur at the inlet of swirling jet because of the high turbulence intensity at the surfaces of the channel. Increasing inlet temperature from $T_{inlet}=5^{\circ}C$ to $30^{\circ}C$ has not a significant effect on average Nusselt number. Numerical model was also verified with some correlation and experimental results of literature.

INTRODUCTION

The present study is focused on the numerical investigation of heat transfer from a heated surface by using nanofluids and swirling jets. A nanofluid is defined as a suspension of solid particles which have 1-100 nm size in a base fluid. In heat transfer applications using nanofluid, the particles suspended in the base fluid, expand the thermal capacity of the fluid. Interactions and collisions between particles cause to increase in turbulence and turbulence intensity of the transition surface. Turbulence intensity and large surface area enable more heat transfer. Nanoparticles carry 20% of

their atoms at the surface that makes them ready to heat transfer. Another advantage of using nanofluids is the particle agitation cause micro-convection in the fluid due to its very small size and therefore increases the heat transfer in particular heat transfer from surfaces with high heat flux, as well as industry, medicine and space research. But the main disadvantages of using nanofluid may be a pressure drop and particle deposition in pipes or ducts. So, using nanofluids with swirling jets may be a key solution for these disadvantages.

Corresponding author. Afsin Gungor*

E-mail address: afsingungor@hotmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525050>

This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

One of the main problems with the design parameter for new technological devices is heat loads. Using swirling flow with nanofluids can be a key solution to solve this heat loads problem. So, swirling flows have gained an increasing interest in the last decade in fluid dynamics research, since in many technical applications swirl is an essential phenomenon. Swirling flows are generally used in the industry for separation, mixing and flame stabilization. The main characteristic of swirling flow is the combination of axial and tangential velocities. Swirling flows are used to minimize pressure drop and prevent particle deposition [1]. In swirling flows, part of the fluid enters axially while the remainder is injected tangentially at various locations along the tube axis. The radial pressure gradient results in thinning of thermal boundary layer with an accompanying improvement in heat transfer [2]. Many studies on enhancing heat transfer technique as impinging jets or swirling jets with different coolant can be found in the literature. Kilic et al. [3, 4] surveyed the cooling of a flat plate with the support of the impinging fluid air jet for different Reynolds numbers and dimensionless channel heights. Teamah et al. [5] investigated heat transfer and flow structure formed by Al₂O₃ nanofluid to flat plate by experimentally and numerically with various Re number and the different volume ratio of nanofluids. Sun et al. [6] researched the effect of a single impinging jet using Cu-water nanofluids as working fluid on heat transfer. Kilic et al. [7] investigated the heat transfer from high heat flux surfaces for different parameters using nanofluids and multiple impinging jets. It was found that the increase in Re number and decrease in particle diameter causes an increase in heat transfer. Sekrani et al. [8] investigated turbulent convective heat transfer of Al₂O₃ nanofluid flowing in a circular tube with uniform heat flux for different turbulence model numerically. Wongcharee et al. [9] investigated effects of swirling impinging jets with TiO₂-water nanofluid on heat transfer for different jet-to-target spacing ratio, Reynolds number and volume concentration. Akyurek et al. [10] studied turbulent forced convection heat transfer and pressure drop characteristic of Al₂O₃-water nanofluid experimentally by using wire coil turbulators. Kilic [11, 12] studied on combined effects of nanofluid and swirling jets on heat transfer. He obtained that increasing Reynolds number and volume ratio cause an increase on heat transfer. This study is different from the studies at literature by evaluating the combined effect of swirling jets and nanofluids on heat transfer for different parameters to prevent the disadvantages of nanofluids. By using the combined effect of nanofluids and swirling flows heat transfer enhancement was evaluated for different Reynolds number and different inlet temperature. Numerical results

were also validated with the experimental results in the literature.

NUMERICAL MODEL

The computational domain consists of a rectangular channel of which dimensions are 10x10x50 mm. Two jet inlets of which dimensions are 3x3 mm were located at the inverse direction to inject tangentially. There is one outlet at the end of the channel. All walls have a constant wall temperature. Inlet velocity of swirling jets is applied according to the Reynolds number. k- ω turbulence model of PHOENICS CFD code was used for this numerical analysis. CFD simulation domain is shown in Fig.1 Mesh structure is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 1. CFD Simulation model

Figure 2. Mesh Structure

The continuity, Reynolds averaged momentum and time-averaged energy equations governing 3-dimensional steady, the flow of fluid with constant properties used for turbulent solutions can be written in the Cartesian coordinate system as follows;

Continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Momentum equation:

$$\rho U_i \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \rho u_i' u_j' \right] \quad (2)$$

Energy equation:

$$\rho c_p U_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} - \rho c_p u_i' T' \right] \quad (3)$$

Since Reynold number is higher than 10000. It was assumed that fluid is turbulent. So, a $k-\omega$ turbulent model of PHOENICS computational fluid dynamics code was used for numerical analysis. $k-\omega$ turbulence model involves the solution of transport equations for the turbulent kinetic energy k and the turbulence frequency ω . ω can be defined as the specific dissipation rate ε/k where ε is the dissipation rate of k . In this study, a $k-\omega$ turbulence model is preferred since it performs better in transitional flows and in flows with adverse pressure gradients. Additionally, the model is numerically very stable; it means this model can produce converged solutions more rapidly than the other models. All boundary conditions used in the study are summarized in Table 1. It was used $100 \times 30 \times 32$ (96000 elements) meshes for this application. Mesh structure was prepared according to flow conditions. In order to get more precise numerical results, we intensified mesh numbers in some region as a jet inlet region and the surface of walls. Sweep number was studied between 2000 and 6000 and cell number was also studied between 24 and 36. It is observed that numerical geometry was independent of sweep number and cell number when sweep number was 3000 and cell number was $100 \times 30 \times 32$.

Table 1. Boundary Conditions

	U (m/s)	V (m/s)	W (m/s)	T (°C)	k	ω
Inlet	U=0	V=V _{inlet}	W=0	T=T _{inlet}	k= (I.V _{inlet})	$\omega = \varepsilon / (Cd.k)$
Outlet	$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} = 0$	$\frac{\partial V}{\partial y} = 0$	$\frac{\partial W}{\partial z} = 0$	T=T _{outlet}	$\frac{\partial k}{\partial z} = 0$	$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} = 0$
Bottom Wall	U=0	V=0	W=0	T=T _{surface}	$k = U\tau^2 / \sqrt{C_d}$	$\omega = U\tau / (\sqrt{C_d} \cdot \kappa \cdot \delta)$
Top Wall	U=0	V=0	W=0	T=T _{surface}	$k = U\tau^2 / \sqrt{C_d}$	$\omega = U\tau / (\sqrt{C_d} \cdot \kappa \cdot \delta)$
Front and Backwall	U=0	V=0	W=0	T=T _{surface}	$k = U\tau^2 / \sqrt{C_d}$	$\omega = U\tau / (\sqrt{C_d} \cdot \kappa \cdot \delta)$

where $U\tau$ is the resultant friction velocity ($U\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w / \rho}$), τ_w is the wall shear stress, δ is the normal distance of the first grid point from the wall, and k is von Karman's constant. Additionally, V_{inlet} is the bulk inlet velocity, I is the turbulent intensity (typically in the range $0.01 < I < 0.05$), ε is the dissipation rate ($\varepsilon = Cd^{3/4} \cdot k^{3/2} / L_m$), Cd is the constant ($Cd = 0.09$) and the mixing length $L_m \sim 0.1H$, where H is a characteristic inlet dimension. Numerical results were verified with the experimental results of Sunder and Sharma [13] and correlation of Petukhov, Gnielinsky, Dittus and Boelter [8]. Verification of numerical model is shown in Fig.3. Difference between numerical results and experimental results is less than 11% for $Re = 12000 - 18000$.

Figure 3. Verification of the model with experimental results and correlations

The heat transfer from the surfaces to the fluid will take place by convection, conduction and radiation.

$$\dot{Q}_{convection} = \dot{Q}_{total} - \dot{Q}_{conduction} - \dot{Q}_{radiation} \quad (4)$$

Heat transfer occurs from high-temperature walls to the nanofluid. So, heat transfer rate gained by nanofluid equals the heat transfer rate lost by walls. As a result, walls surfaces will be cooled by using nanofluid with swirling jet. It is assumed that channel walls have a constant temperature. So, heat conduction through the walls (from the outer surface to the inner surface) is neglected. Heat transfer with radiation is negligible in this study because the surface temperature is under 573.15 K.

Heat transfer rate gained by the fluid from wall surfaces;

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m} \cdot C_{p(nf)} \cdot (T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}) \quad (5)$$

Where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate of nanofluid, $C_{p(nf)}$ is nanofluid specific heat, T_{outlet} is the outlet temperature of nanofluid and T_{inlet} is the inlet temperature of nanofluid. Nusselt number (Nu) is a dimensionless parameter indicating the ratio of heat transfer with convection to heat transfer with conduction. The average Nusselt number can be presented as the ratio of the average heat transfer coefficient times characteristic length (D_h) to the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the nanofluid.

$$Nu_{avg} = \frac{h_{avg} \cdot D_h}{k_{nf}} \quad (6)$$

Where h_{avg} is the average heat transfer coefficient, measured, D_h is the hydraulic diameter, and k_{nf} is the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the nanofluid. Average heat transfer coefficient can be presented as;

$$h_{avg} = \dot{Q}/(A_s \cdot T_{lm}) \quad (7)$$

Where A_s is the convection surface area and T_{lm} is the logarithmic mean temperature of nanofluid.

$$T_{lm} = (\Delta T_e - \Delta T_i) / \ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_e}{\Delta T_i}\right) \quad (8)$$

Where ΔT_e is the temperature difference between surface temperature and nanofluid exit temperature ($\Delta T_e = (T_s - T_e)$) and ΔT_i is temperature difference between surface temperature and nanofluid inlet temperature ($\Delta T_i = (T_s - T_i)$). Reynolds number (Re) is used to determine for forced convection whether the flow is laminar or turbulent. Reynolds number based on turbulent flow;

$$Re = \frac{(\rho_{nf} \cdot V_{jet} \cdot D_h)}{(\mu_{nf})} \quad (9)$$

Where ρ_{nf} is the nanofluid density, V_{jet} is the jet velocity, and μ_{nf} is the nanofluid dynamic viscosity.

The density of nanofluids is;

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \varphi) \cdot \rho_{bf} + \varphi \cdot \rho_p \quad (10)$$

Where ρ_{bf} is the base fluid (water) density, φ is the volumetric ratio of the nanofluid, and ρ_p is the density of the solid particles in the nanofluid. The volumetric ratio of nanoparticles is;

$$\varphi = \frac{1}{(1/\omega) \cdot (\rho_p - \rho_{bf})} \quad (11)$$

Where ω is the density difference between the fluid and the main fluid (water). The nanofluid specific heat is calculated from;

$$C_{p_{nf}} = \frac{\varphi \cdot (\rho \cdot C_p)_p + (1 - \varphi) \cdot (\rho \cdot C_p)_f}{(\rho_{nf})} \quad (12)$$

Where $C_{p(p)}$ is the specific heat of particle $C_{p(f)}$ is the specific heat of base fluid. The effective thermal conductivity of nanofluid is calculated according to Coercion [14];

$$\frac{k_{eff}}{k_f} = 1 + 4.4 Re^{0.4} Pr^{0.66} \left(\frac{T_{nf}}{T_{fr}}\right)^{10} \left(\frac{k_p}{k_f}\right)^{0.03} \varphi^{0.66} \quad (13)$$

Where Re is the nanoparticle Reynolds number, Pr is the Prandtl number of the base liquid. k_p is the nanoparticle

thermal conductivity, φ is the volume ratio of the suspended nanoparticles, T_{nf} is the nanofluid temperature (K), T_{fr} is the freezing point of the base liquid. Nanoparticle Reynolds number is defined as;

$$Re = \frac{2\rho_b k_b T}{\pi \mu_b^2 d_p} \quad (14)$$

k_b is the Boltzmann's constant. The effective dynamic viscosity of nanofluids defined as;

$$\mu_{nf} = \mu_{bf} (1 + 2,5 \varphi + 4,698 \varphi^2) \quad (15)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, numerical results were prepared for two parameters. Effects of Al_2O_3 -water nanofluid with 20 nm particle diameter and volume ratio of $\varphi=4\%$ on heat transfer for different Reynolds number ($Re=12000, 15000, 18000, 21000$), different inlet different inlet temperature ($T_{inlet}=5, 10, 20, 30^\circ C$) were obtained.

3.1. Effects of different Reynolds number on heat transfer

To understand the effect of fluid velocity on heat transfer, the Reynolds number was increased from $Re=12000$ to 21000 . Fig.4 and Fig.5. show velocity vector and temperature contours of fluid flow at the midpoint of the inlet of swirling jet, in the middle of channel and outlet of the channel at x-direction ($x/D_h=0.03, 8, 16$) for $Re=12000$ and 21000 respectively.

Figure 4. Velocity vectors for different Reynolds Number (a) $Re=12000$ and (b) $Re=21000$

Thermal boundary region does not occur at the inlet of swirling jet because of the high turbulence intensity at the surfaces of the channel. Temperature increase can be seen only in the impinging region of swirling jet because fluid velocity decreases at this region.

Figure 5. Temperature contours for different Reynolds Number (a) Re=12000 and (b) Re= 21000

Velocity vector occurs in a shape of a flattened sphere. So, the effect of swirling jet can be seen significantly at the inlet region of swirling jets. In the middle of the channel thermal boundary layer is thickening because of the velocity decrease (decrease of the hydrodynamic boundary layer) at the corner of the rectangular channel. This boundary layer thickness increase can be seen at the direction of swirling flow. Because separation of fluid flow is more evident in this region. At the end of the channel, a decrease of fluid velocity can be seen easily. Separation of the fluid flow is more important at the corner of the channel at this region. Decreasing hydrodynamic boundary layer thickness causes an increase in thermal boundary layer thickness and it causes an increase in surface temperature. So increasing Reynolds number causes an increase in the hydrodynamic boundary layer and a decrease of the thermal boundary layer and surface temperature. Variation of average Nusselt number for different Reynolds number is shown in Fig.6.

Figure 6. Average Nusselt Number of Al₂O₃-H₂O nanofluid for different Reynolds Number

It is obtained that increasing Reynolds number causes an increase in the average Nusselt number and decrease in surface temperature. So, increasing Reynolds number from Re=12000 to 21000 causes an increase of 51.3% on average Nusselt Number. But this increase decreases gradually.

Increasing Reynolds number from Re=12000 to 15000 causes an increase of 17.2% on the average Nusselt number. But the increase in Reynolds number from Re=15000 to 18000 and Re=18000 to 21000, the inclination decreases to 14.3% and 12.9% respectively.

3.2. Effects of different inlet temperature on heat transfer

Fig.7 shows average Nusselt number for different inlet temperature ($T_{inlet} = 5, 10, 20, 30^{\circ}C$) of Al₂O₃-H₂O when it is used at 20 nm particle size and $\phi=4\%$ at Re=18000. It can be seen that increasing inlet temperature has not a considerable effect on average Nusselt number. The reason of this is increasing or decreasing the inlet temperature causes a change on heat convection coefficient.

Fig. 7. Average Nusselt numbers of Al₂O₃-H₂O nanofluid for different inlet temperature

This means that heat flux from the surface to the fluid changes temperature difference between bulk fluid temperature and average surface temperature. So, surface temperature can be change but it does not cause a significant change on average Nusselt number. Temperature contours for different inlet temperature are shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8. Temperature contours of Al₂O₃-H₂O nanofluid for different inlet temperature (a) $T_{inlet} = 5^{\circ}C$ and (b) $T_{inlet} = 30^{\circ}C$

CONCLUSIONS

The present study is focused on the numerical investigation of heat transfer from a heated surface by using nanofluids and swirling jets. Effects of different Reynolds number, and different inlet temperature on heat transfer and fluid flow were studied numerically. It is obtained that increasing Reynolds number from $Re=12000$ to 21000 causes an increase of 51.3% on average Nusselt Number. Increasing inlet temperature from $T_{inlet}=5^{\circ}C$ to $30^{\circ}C$ has not a significant effect on average Nusselt number. Difference between numerical results of this study and experimental results is less than 11% for $Re=12000-18000$. Research areas for future investigations can be using different particle diameter, different volume ratio and different types of nanofluids with different application geometries and cooling techniques.

Nomenclature

$C_{p_{nf}}$	Nanofluid specific heat [Jkg-1K-1]
C_{p_p}	Particle specific heat [Jkg-1K-1]
k_{eff}	Effective thermal conductivity [Wm-1K-1]
k_{nf}	Nanofluid thermal conductivity [Wm-1K-1]
Nu_x	Local Nusselt number [$Nu_x=Q.Dh\Delta T-1.k_{nf}-1$]
Nu_{avg}	Average Nusselt number [$Nu_{avg}=h_{avg}.Dh.k_{nf}-1$]
Greek Symbols	
ρ_{bf}	Base fluid density [kgm-3]
ϕ	Nanoparticle volume ratio
μ_{nf}	Nanofluid dynamic viscosity [kg.m-1. s-1]

REFERENCES

- [1] Kharoua, N., Khezzar L., Alshehhi M., The interaction of confined swirling flow with conical bluff body: numerical simulation, *Chemical engineering research and design*, 136 (2018), pp.207-218.
- [2] Chang F., Dhir VK., Heat transfer enhancement and turbulent flow field in tangentially injected swirl flows in tubes, *American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Heat Transfer Division*, 256 (1993), pp.37-48.
- [3] Kilic, M., Calisir, T., Baskaya, S., Experimental and numerical study of heat transfer from a heated flat plate in a rectangular channel with an impinging Jet, *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, 39 (2017), 1, pp. 329-344.
- [4] Kilic, M., Baskaya, S., Improvement of heat transfer from high heat flux surfaces by using vortex promoters with different geometries and impinging jets, *Journal of the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture of Gazi University*, 32(3) (2017), pp.693-707.
- [5] Teamah, M. A., Dawood, M.M., Shehata, A., Numerical and experimental investigation of flow structure and behavior of nanofluids flow impingement on horizontal flat plate, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 74 (2016), pp. 235-246.
- [6] Sun, B., Qu, Y., Yang, D., Heat transfer of Single Impinging jet with Cu nanofluids, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 102 (2016), pp.701-707.
- [7] Kilic, M., Ali H.M., Numerical investigation of combined effect of nanofluids and multiple impinging jets on heat transfer, *Thermal Science*, (2018), doi.org/10.2298/TSCII171204094K.
- [8] Sekrani, G., Poncet, S., Proulx, P., Modelling of convective turbulent heat transfer of water-based Al₂O₃ nanofluids in a uniformly heated pipe, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 176 (2018), pp.205-219.
- [9] Wongcharee, K., Chuwattanakul, V., Eiamsa-ard, S., Heat transfer of swirling impinging jets with TiO₂-water nanofluids, *Chem. Eng. and Processing*, 114 (2017), pp.16-23.
- [10] Akyurek, E.F., Geliş, K., Şahin, B., Manay, E., Experimental Analysis of nanofluid with wire coil turbulators in a concentric tube heat exchanger, *Results in Physics*, 9 (2018), pp. 376-389.
- [11] Kilic M., Investigation of heat transfer for different types of nanofluids with swirling jets, ZEUGMA I. Uluslararası Multi Disipliner Çalışmalar Kongresi 13-16 Eylül 2018, Gaziantep.
- [12] Kilic M., Numerical investigation of heat transfer on a heated surface with effects of nanofluids and swirling jets, ZEUGMA I. Uluslararası Multi Disipliner Çalışmalar Kongresi, 13-16 Eylül 2018, Gaziantep.
- [13] Sundar, L.S., Sharma, K.V., Heat transfer enhancements of low volume concentration Al₂O₃ nanofluid and with longitudinal strip inserts in a circular tube, *Int.J. of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 53 (2010), pp. 4280-4286.
- [14] Coercions, M., Empirical correlating equations for predicting the effective thermal conductivity and dynamic viscosity of nanofluids, *Energy Conversation Management*, 52 (2011), 1, pp.789-93.

